

Exploring the pharmacological mechanism of Qishen Yiqi dropping pills in treating chronic heart failure based on network pharmacology and molecular docking

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Abstract

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is a severe condition that affects millions of people worldwide. Despite standardized treatments, patients often face recurrent symptoms such as dyspnea, edema, and fatigue, which impair their quality of life and contribute to high mortality and hospital readmission rates. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) offers alternative therapies, and Qishen Yiqi Dropping Pills (QYDP) has emerged as a potential treatment for CHF. QYDP is composed of Danshen, Huangqi, Jiangxiang, and Sanqi and is known for its ability to promote circulation, enhance Qi, and support cardiac health. Although clinical studies have suggested that QYDP can alleviate CHF symptoms, the underlying molecular mechanisms are not fully understood. In this study, network pharmacology and molecular docking were used to explore the pharmacological targets of QYDP for CHF treatment. Four core genes were identified: *AKT1*, *HIF1A*, *STAT3*, and *MYC*. Molecular docking confirmed the interactions between these genes and active compounds in QYDP, such as kaempferol, luteolin, quercetin, tanshinone IIa, and cryptotanshinone. These findings suggest that QYDP may treat CHF through a multitarget mechanism, offering new insights into its therapeutic potential and providing a basis for further clinical research.

Keywords

CHF, cardiovascular disease, QYDP, traditional Chinese medicine

Introduction

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is a challenging and multifaceted clinical syndrome characterized by progressive deterioration of cardiac structure and function due to various factors (Ponikowski et al. 2016). Statistics indicate that by 2019, the number of reported heart failure cases worldwide had increased to approximately 56.19 million (Liu et

al. 2024). Patients with CHF and patients with malignant tumors are similar in their 5-year survival rates (Lam et al. 2011). In recent years, the “fantastic four” drugs, beta-blockers, angiotensin receptor/neprilysin, sodium-glucose cotransporter-2, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, have been used in clinical practice to treat patients with CHF (Bauersachs 2021; Bauersachs and Soltani 2023; Chinese

Society of Cardiology et al. 2024). However, the prolonged use of these medications may result in a number of side effects, including electrolyte imbalance, hypotension, and fluid loss, necessitating the use of different medications for CHF treatment (Chinese Society of Cardiology et al. 2024). Therefore, there is an urgent need to identify adjunctive therapies to further improve the mortality rate of CHF, especially in patients with concomitant hypotension. (Greene et al. 2020; Liang and Gu 2021; He et al. 2023; Chinese Society of Cardiology et al. 2024).

Qishen Yiqi Dropping Pills (QYDP) have been widely used for the treatment of CHF because they can improve certain symptoms caused by insufficient Qi and blood as a type of Traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), renowned for having few adverse effects and long-lasting benefits (Hao et al. 2015). Many randomized controlled clinical trials (RCTs) have shown that QYDP is an efficient and safe treatment for persistent cardiovascular diseases (Chen et al. 2021). QYDP is composed of Danshen (*Radix Salviae*), Huangqi (*Hedysarum multijugum* Maxim), Jiangxiang (*Dalbergia odorifera* [Lignum]), and Sanqi (*Panax notoginseng*). Various herbal treatments offer therapeutic benefits for heart failure, particularly following acute myocardial infarction. For instance, *Salvia miltiorrhiza* helps alleviate inflammatory damage in heart failure by regulating the MD2/TLR4-MyD88 complex and the TLR4-TRAF6-NF- κ B signaling pathway (Wang et al. 2020). Similarly, *Astragalus mongholicus* improves heart failure by modulating extracellular vesicle miR-27a-3p derived from pericardial adipose tissue, which activates AMPK α 2-mediated mitophagy (Chen et al. 2024). Additionally, *Panax notoginseng* saponins protect against both acute myocardial infarction and heart failure by inducing autophagy (Wang et al. 2021).

Collectively, these findings highlight the pharmacological effects of QYDP in treating CHF. Several studies have shown that QYDP protects the myocardium in rats with CHF by enhancing cardiac angiogenesis, reducing myocardial fibrosis, improving cardiomyocyte hypertrophy, and inhibiting myocardial apoptosis (Lu et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2019; Chen et al. 2022); however, the specific pharmacological pathways through which QYDP exerts its effects in CHF remain unclear. Network pharmacology is an extremely powerful and innovative approach to elucidate the mechanisms of action of TCM at the molecular level (Zhang et al. 2013; Xu et al. 2020). This study was designed using network pharmacology and molecular docking to systematically search for the core target genes of the QYDP in treating CHF.

Materials and methods

Target preacquisition

The traditional Chinese medicine systems pharmacology database and analysis platform (TCMSP) was used to

identify the active QYDP constituents (Ru et al. 2014). Using UniProt, the gene targets of the identified compounds were determined (UniProt Consortium T 2017). We identified genes related to “chronic heart failure” from GeneCards (Zhou et al. 2024), OMIM (Amberger and Hamosh 2017), TTD (Barbarino et al. 2018), and PharmGKB databases. Overlapping genes were removed using the Venn package, and a final set of candidate genes associated with CHF was obtained.

Network construction

The Venn package (Jia et al. 2021) was used to determine the intersection of genes related to CHF and the active compounds of QYDP. The STRING database was used to analyze the intersecting genes and create a protein interaction network, using “humans” as the target species and a combined score of > 0.95 (Szklarczyk et al. 2023). Gene Ontology (GO) functional (Gene Ontology Consortium et al. 2012) and Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway enrichment analyses (Kanehisa et al. 2017) were conducted for these genes using the screening criterion ($q < 0.05$) (Yu et al. 2012).

Network characterization and key gene acquisition

To further explore the network characteristics of the protein-protein interaction (PPI), we used the STRING database and CytoNCA plugin in Cytoscape 3.8.0 software (Tang et al. 2015). Key genes in this network were screened based on six parameters: 1) betweenness centrality (BC), 2) closeness centrality (CC), 3) degree centrality (DC), 4) eigenvector centrality, 5) local average connectivity-based method centrality, and 6) network centrality. We obtained key nodes (genes) based on their network scores and retained the genes whose expression was greater than the median value.

Molecular docking

For molecular docking, we collected the core chemical compounds of QYDP and selected the core genes from gene enrichment and network characteristic analyses. We obtained the 2D structures of these compounds using PubChem (Kim 2016) and converted them into 3D chemical structures using ChemOffice software. PDB was used to obtain the 3D structure of the core gene proteins (Burley et al. 2017). Water molecules and protein molecular ligands were removed using PyMol (Rosignoli and Paiardini 2022). The format of the core chemical compounds and core gene proteins was converted into pdbqt format, and their active pockets were determined using AutoDock Vina and AutoDockTools 1.5.6 software. Molecular docking data were generated using AutoDock Vina according to their active pockets. Finally, the 3D

structures of the molecular docking were visualized using PyMol software. To validate the molecular docking method, a compound known to bind to target proteins was selected as a positive control.

Results

Target acquisition

Compounds in QYDP and corresponding target genes

A total of 108 active QYDP constituents were identified: 65 from Danshen, 20 from Huangqi, 15 from Jiangxiang, and eight from Sanqi. A total of 2390 target genes associated with the active compounds of QYDP were identified, including 932 target genes of Danshen, 953 target genes of Huangqi, 252 target genes of Jiangxiang, and 253 target genes of Sanqi. Ultimately, we obtained 1631 target genes. A total of 218 gene targets were obtained after the deletion of duplicate genes, as shown in Fig. 1.

Genes related to CHF

After removing the overlapping genes, we obtained a total of 2915 genes related to CHF, including 2818 genes from the GeneCards database (the screening criterion was a relevance score > 10), 152 genes from the DrugBank database, 268 genes from the OMIM database, 16 genes from the PharmGKB database, and 13 genes from the TTD database (Fig. 2).

Network construction

Intersection of genes related to CHF and genes associated with QYDP

After eliminating duplicate genes using the R language Venn package, 218 therapeutic gene targets for QYDP and 2915 disease-related gene targets for CHF were identified. As illustrated in Fig. 3, we identified 157 intersecting genes linked to the active ingredients in QYDP that were associated with CHF.

PPI network of the disease and drug target genes

The results of the PPI analysis of the 157 intersecting genes show that a total of 117 genes were found to interact with other proteins (Fig. 4).

GO enrichment analysis

From the GO enrichment analysis of the intersecting genes, we obtained 2283 biological processes, 218 molecular functions, and 77 cellular components using a screening criterion of a q value < 0.05. The top ten terms were visualized according to the q value (Fig. 5).

KEGG pathway enrichment analysis

We obtained 162 pathways using a screening criterion of a q value < 0.05 from the KEGG pathway enrichment analysis. According to the q value, the top 30 KEGG items were visualized, as shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 1. Gene targets for QYDP compounds.

Figure 2. Gene targets of the CHF from the databases.

Figure 3. One hundred and fifty-seven overlapping genes between QYDP and CHF.

Acquisition of key genes based on network characteristics analysis

Based on six parameters of the CytoNCA plugin, a PPI network of 117 overlapping genes was constructed using two filters. We acquired 36 nodes (genes) and 151 edges using the first filter (Fig. 7A). Using the second filter, we identified 12 core genes: *CDKN1A*, *STAT3*, *JUN*, *AKT1*, *HIF1A*, *MAPK1*, *RBI*, *TP53*, *MAPK14*, *CCND1*, *MYC*, and *RELA* (Fig. 7B, C).

Molecular docking

We selected the core compounds of QYDP, namely kaempferol, luteolin, quercetin, tanshinone IIa, and cryptotanshinone, and four genes for molecular docking, namely *HIF1A*, *MYC*, *STAT3*, and *AKT1*. Combining the results of network characteristics and gene enrichment analyses, as shown in Table 1, Fig. 8. Trimetazidine, a compound experimentally validated to bind to the aforementioned

targets, was used as a positive control. The validation results indicated favorable molecular docking interactions between trimetazidine and *AKT1*, *Myc*, *HIF-1 α* , and *STAT3* using the aforementioned method, as illustrated in Table 2, Fig. 9.

Table 1. The molecular docking results in the compounds of QYDP and four core genes.

Number	Core targets	Compounds	Docking affinity (kcal/mol)
1	AKT1	kaempferol	-8.1
		Luteolin	-8.2
		Quercetin	-8.2
2	Myc	Quercetin	-6.2
		tanshinone IIa	-7.4
3	HIF1A	Quercetin	-8.0
4	STAT3	cryptotanshinone	-7.6

Table 2. The molecular docking results in the trimetazidine and four core genes.

Number	Core genes	Compound	Docking affinity (kcal/mol)
1	AKT1	trimetazidine	-6.6
2	Myc	trimetazidine	-5.1
3	HIF1A	trimetazidine	-5.4
4	STAT3	trimetazidine	-4.8

Discussion

Previous research has demonstrated that CHF patient mortality is increasing globally, and optimizing CHF treatment may improve patient survival rates (Crowley et al. 2017; Lin et al. 2017; Yohannes et al. 2017). Based on practical clinical applications and related clinical studies, QYDP can improve cardiac function in patients with CHF (Chang et al. 2019; Mao et al. 2020; Wang et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2021; He et al. 2023; Xingmeng et al. 2023). Existing pharmacological mechanism studies show that QYDP improves cardiac function by regulating long non-coding RNA *TINCR* (Chen et al. 2022) or *XIST* gene (Luo et al. 2022) expression. Some studies have investigated the potential mechanism of QYDP by examining the expression of proteins such as Bax, VEGF (Wang et al. 2019), caspase-3, α -SMA, and TGF- β 1 (Lu et al. 2019). However, it is unclear whether there are more pharmacological routes by which QYDP treats CHF. Network pharmacology studies make it possible to further identify the target genes and proteins of QYDP therapy in CHF.

According to our network pharmacology investigation, QYDP improved cardiac function through multiple targets and pathways. Moreover, we also observed some targets that have been experimentally verified to be related to the efficacy of QYDP, such as Bax, VEGF, and caspase-3, although the corresponding genes of the above proteins were excluded during the screening of the key genes, confirming to a certain extent that our study has reference value for the discovery of the pharmacological effects of QYDP in CHF. GO analysis revealed that the majority of the overlapping genes were responsible for phosphatase

Figure 4. 117 genes interacting with other proteins from the results of the PPI network.

binding, oxidative stress, and other processes. According to KEGG analysis, fluid shear stress, atherosclerosis, and the TNF, IL-17, and PI3K-Akt signaling pathways were the major enriched pathways for the overlapping genes. Overall, network pharmacology revealed 12 key genes, including *CDKN1A*, *JUN*, *MAPK1*, *RB1*, *TP53*, *MAPK14*, *CCND1*, and *RELA*, and in particular, *STAT3*, *HIF1A*, *MYC*, and *AKT1*.

All four core gene targets have proven roles in CHF treatment. The signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (*STAT3*) is necessary for several biological processes, notably cell proliferation and death. According to a previous study, astragaloside IV can reduce HF through the JAK-*STAT3* pathway (Sui et al. 2019). The *MYC* proto-oncogene (also known as *MYC* or *c-Myc*) contributes to cellular transformation and cell cycle progression (Thompson 1998; Gomes et al. 2017). Analysis

of GSE1145 microarray data revealed that *MYC* is closely related to heart failure (Chen et al. 2013). The Wnt/ β -catenin/*c-myc* axis is closely related to abnormal cardiac remodeling and can prevent and treat heart failure (Hou et al. 2017). *AKT* serine/threonine kinase 1 (*AKT1*) controls various cellular processes such as angiogenesis, metabolism, cell division, and survival. A previous study reported that cardiac function was improved by regulating the angiogenic regulatory network via *AKT1* induction in endothelial cells (Schiekofer et al. 2008). According to a previous study, sphingosylphosphorylcholine uses the lipid raft/*PTEN*/*Akt1*/*mTOR*-mediated autophagy to shield cardiomyocytes from ischemia-induced death (Yue et al. 2015). Apoptosis, energy metabolism, and angiogenesis are significantly affected by hypoxia-inducible factor-1 subunit alpha (*HIF1A*), a subunit of *HIF-1*. Muscone enhanced angiogenesis by upregulating *HIF-1 α* and *VEGFA*

Figure 5. The GO enrichment results of the top 10 terms.

Figure 6. The top 30 KEGG pathway enrichment results.

Figure 7. PPI network of overlapping genes (yellow squares highlight important genes). **A** PPI network of the 117 overlapping genes; **B** The 36 genes obtained using the first filter of the CytoNCA plugin; **C** The acquisition of 12 key genes using the second filter of the CytoNCA plugin.

Figure 8. Results of active chemicals binding to putative target proteins using molecular docking.

Figure 9. Results of the positive control, trimetazidine binding to putative target proteins using molecular docking.

expression, which in turn improved heart function (Du et al. 2018). Silter et al. (2010) reported that HIF-1 α has a major part in protecting cardiac function against chronic pressure overload.

In this study, quercetin, kaempferol, luteolin, tanshinone IIA, and cryptotanshinone were screened from the compounds of QYDP using the TCMSP based on their better OB and DL. Many studies have shown that these compounds have anti-apoptotic, antioxidative, and anti-inflammatory effects. The TNF and the PI3K-Akt pathway are involved in treating multiple cardiovascular diseases with quercetin (Muhammad and Fatima 2015; Patel et al. 2018; Guo et al. 2019). Kaempferol is a flavonoid with both anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. According to a report, kaempferol shields cardiomyocytes from heart failure by regulating the NF- κ B/mitogen-activated protein kinase and AMPK/Nrf2 pathways (Zhang et al. 2019). Luteolin has been reported to improve cardiac function by adjusting sarcoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺-ATPase 2a levels in rats with heart failure (Hu et al. 2017). Tanshinone IIA regulates angiogenesis, inflammation resistance, and antioxidant activity and has anti-apoptotic effects (Gao et al. 2019; Zhao et al. 2019; Zhou et al. 2019). Although there is little research on the role of cryptotanshinone in heart failure, a study reported that cryptotanshinone can inhibit STAT3, resulting in the blockade of the NF- κ B pathway (He et al. 2019).

Trimetazidine directly improves myocardial metabolism in both clinical and basic studies (Kantor et al. 2000). Therefore, trimetazidine was used as a positive control to validate the molecular docking method for active compounds of QYDP. The results showed that the propensity of core targets to bind kaempferol, luteolin, tanshinone IIA, quercetin, and cryptotanshinone was similar to that for trimetazidine. In brief, the findings of this study showed that AKT1, Myc, HIF-1 α , and STAT3 may be the core targets of QYDP in treating cardiovascular disease. Nevertheless, this study was based on a network pharmacology method to mine and analyze the data. In the future, we plan to perform further clinical validation of the role of QYDP in CHF.

Conclusions

This network pharmacology study provides evidence for the use of QYDP in the treatment of CHF by identifying potential targets and providing insights into the mechanisms of action of QYDP in the treatment of CHF. AKT1, Myc, HIF1A, and STAT3 are potential targets of QYDP in CHF treatment, highlighting the potential of QYDP as an alternative and complementary therapy. Further experimental validation is warranted to confirm these findings and to elucidate the specific roles of the identified targets and pathways.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

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